

FABRICATION OF TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITE BLADE

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SUMMARY: Low cost fabrication process for titanium matrix composite (TMC) blade was newly developed using a superplastic-formable SCS-6/SP-700 (SiC/Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Fe-2Mo mass%) composite panel. This process consists of three steps: (i) consolidation of a flat TMC panel in an average thickness of 20mm, (ii) superplastic forming to twist the panel and (iii) machining to a final configuration. Using this 3-step process, the TMC blades were successfully fabricated without any defects. Production cost of the TMC blade can be reduced to 20% of the cost in the conventional fabrication process, foil-filament method, which requires the preliminary forming of titanium alloy foils and the elaborate tooling for the net-shaped consolidation. A load-controlled high cycle fatigue test of the TMC blade was conducted under a stress amplitude of 294MPa and a stress ratio (R) = -1 at room temperature. After the loading of 3×10^7 cycles, no cracks were observed on the surface of the TMC blade by means of a liquid penetrant test.

KEYWORDS : Titanium Matrix Composite, Production Cost, Superplastic Forming, Blade, High Cycle Fatigue, SCS-6, SP-700

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites (TMCs) are attractive for aerospace structural applications, because of their high specific strength and stiffness [1, 2]. However, the enormous production cost of TMCs, resulting from preliminary forming and elaborate tooling for consolidation, is a serious impediment to their practical application. One of the promising approaches to reducing the production cost is to apply a superplastic forming (SPF) technique in manufacturing TMC parts. A series of superplastic formable TMC sheets, SiC/Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Mo-2Fe mass% (SCS-6/SP-700) composites, were developed, and both their superplastic deformation and the defects generated during this deformation were investigated [3-5]. The diaphragm forming method (DFM) was adopted of a SPF technique to reduce the tensile flow stress generated in the TMC sheet during deformation. Using this technique, TMC blades were successfully fabricated without any observable defects at the fiber/matrix interface [6, 7]. This process consists of six steps: (i) consolidation of a flat TMC sheet of 8.5mm thickness, (ii) pre-contouring, (iii) SPF by DFM, (iv) isothermal forging, (v) diffusion bonding to attach the root

blocks to the deformed TMC, and (vi) machining to the final configuration. However, several un-bonded areas were found in the diffusion bonded interfaces [7].

In this study, an improved fabrication process for the TMC blade has been developed to eliminate the diffusion bonding process. The new process consists of three steps: (i) consolidation of a flat TMC panel of 20mm thickness, (ii) SPF to twist the panel and (iii) machining to a final configuration. Non-destructive inspection and cross-sectional observation were carried out to evaluate the quality of the TMC blade. A load-controlled high cycle fatigue test for the blade was also conducted at room temperature.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 TMC blade model

Schematic of the TMC blade fabricated in this study is shown in Fig.1. Special design requirements of the blade are (i) 25% lighter than a monolithic titanium alloy blade and (ii) structural integrity speed being 115% of an operating speed (*i.e.* 748m/s in tip speed). Fig.2 shows the ratio of average stress in tip speed of 748m/s (σ_A) to fracture strength of the SCS-6/SP-700 composites (σ_F), and the fiber volume fraction (V_f) at normalized height of the TMC blade. The geometry was designed to achieve above two requirements.

Fig.1 Schematic of TMC blade fabricated in this study.

Fig.2 Ratio of average stress in tip speed of 748m/s (σ_A) to fracture strength of the SCS-6/SP-700 composites (σ_F), and the fiber volume fraction (V_f) at normalized height of the TMC blade

2.2 Material and fabrication test of TMC blade

The material used in this study consisted of a new β -rich $\alpha+\beta$ titanium alloy, Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Fe-2Mo mass% (SP-700), reinforced with continuous SiC fiber (SCS-6). The matrix alloy SP-700 shows excellent superplasticity below 1073K [8], and its foils with 200 μ m in nominal thickness were supplied by NKK Corporation (Tokyo, Japan). The reinforcement SCS-6 was produced by Textron Systems, Lowell, MA, and its average diameter is 140 μ m [9]. The SCS-6/SP-700 composite panels with 19 fiber layers were fabricated by foil/fiber/foil process route. The panels with dimensions of 150^w x 280^l x 20^t mm were consolidated for 7.2 ks by hot isostatic pressing at 1048K under Ar-gas pressure of 120MPa. The diaphragm forming to twist the TMC panels was conducted at 1048K under Ar-gas-pressure acting on a driving sheet, SP-700 sheet with 3mm thickness, at a maximum strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The twisted TMC panels were machined to the final configuration, as shown in Fig.1. Non-destructive inspection of the TMC blade was carried out using Xray radiography to check the reinforcement location. Specimens for cross-sectional observation were prepared by wire cutting, and the cut surface of them was polished with a diamond paste of 3 μ m diameter.

2.3 Fatigue test

High cycle fatigue test of the TMC blade was conducted at room temperature to evaluate its resistance under the cyclic loading. The test was carried out under a stress amplitude of 294MPa and a stress ratio (R) = -1. Applied stress during the test was monitored by two strain gages, their location as shown in Fig.3, pasted on the each surface of the TMC blade. The blade was attached to the test apparatus, as shown in Fig.4, and vibrated up to 3×10^7 cycles. After that, the blade was checked by a liquid penetrant test to find the cracks initiated during the fatigue test.

Fig.3 Location of the strain gages pasted on the TMC blade; as indicated by open circles.

Fig.4 Appearance of the fatigue test apparatus

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Blade fabrication

Fig.5 shows the appearance of the specimens when consolidated (Fig.5(a)), after superplastic forming (Fig.5(b)), and after machining (Fig.5(c)). Two TMC blades were successfully fabricated by the 3-step process, and these were used for one for the cross sectional observation and the other for the X-ray radiography and the fatigue test. Un-bonded areas were not observed in the TMC blade, as shown in Fig.6, resulting from the elimination of the diffusion bonding process. Fig.7 shows the X-ray radiographic photograph of the TMC blade, and the SiC fiber position in the blade seems to be almost matched to the design requirement.

Fig.5 Appearance of the specimens (a) when consolidated, (b) after superplastic forming, and (c) after machining.

Fig.6 Cross section of the TMC blade; (a) at the root and (b) at the shank areas.

Fig.7 X-ray radiographic photograph of the TMC blade.

Fig.8 Comparison of the fabrication costs among the conventional (foil-filament method), the 6-step and the 3-step fabrication process for the TMC blade.

3.2 Production cost

Using the 3-step process, production cost of the TMC blade can be reduced to 40% and 20% of the cost in the case of the 6-step process and the conventional process, respectively (Fig.8). The cost was normalized by the total cost in the conventional fabrication process, foil-filament method, which requires the preliminary forming of titanium alloy foils and the elaborate tooling for the net-shape consolidation. In Fig.8, expenses of HIPing and jigs were broken down into 1/10. This cost reduction was mainly due to simplifying the process steps.

3.3 Fatigue test

After the loading of 3×10^7 cycles, no cracks were observed on the surface of the TMC blade by means of a liquid penetrant test. The stress amplitude of 294MPa used in this test was tentatively determined based on the Goodman rule [10] at $R = -1$ utilizing the material data reported by Fujiwara *et al.* [11] for tensile strength of 1540MPa ($V_f=30\%$) and Fukushima *et al.* for fatigue strength of 440 MPa ($R=0.1$, 1×10^6 cycles, $V_f=34\%$)[12]. However, this estimation is temporary and standards of design and evaluation for TMC parts have not been established. Further investigations are required to clarify the relationship between the material data and mechanical properties of TMC parts.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Using superplastic-formable SCS-6/SP-700 (SiC/Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Fe-2Mo mass%) composite panels, titanium matrix composite (TMC) blades were fabricated by means of three-step process, which were newly developed to simplify the TMC blade manufacturing. The quality and the fatigue property of the blades were evaluated with cross-sectional observation, X-ray radiography, and load-controlled high cycle fatigue test. The following results were obtained:

1. Two TMC blades were successfully fabricated without any defects, using the three-step process, which consists of (i) consolidation of a flat TMC panel in an average thickness of 20mm, (ii) superplastic forming to twist the panel and (iii) machining to a final configuration.
2. Production cost of the TMC blade can be reduced to 20% of the cost in the conventional fabrication process, foil-filament method, which requires the preliminary forming of titanium alloy foils and the elaborate tooling for the net-shaped consolidation.
3. A load-controlled high cycle fatigue test of the TMC blade was conducted under a stress amplitude of 294MPa and a stress ratio (R) = -1 at room temperature. After the loading of 3×10^7 cycles, no cracks were observed on the surface of the TMC blade by means of a liquid penetrant test.

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